

Photometric systems for GAIA's Broad Band Photometer

L. Lindegren

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ABSTRACT. Two photometric systems for the GAIA broad-band photometer (BBP) are proposed, assuming that silver coatings will be used in the Astro instrument. System 2B, with five bands covering the spectral region from 350 to 1050 nm, is primarily designed to allow good determination of effective temperatures and reddening. It can be used with a standard CCD sensitivity type (CCD#3) in all bands. System 3B has four broad bands going slightly further towards the UV, plus one intermediate-width band centred on the 510 nm Mg/MgH feature. In order to get sufficient flux in the UV and intermediate bands it needs seven slots and the use of the blue-enhanced sensitivity type (CCD#1B) for some of the bands. The intention is that system 3B might allow determination of additional astrophysical parameters, in particular metallicities.

1 Introduction

The GAIA Broad Band Photometer (BBP) has two functions: (1) it must give sufficient information about the spectral shape for any object observed in Astro in order to calibrate and correct chromaticity in the Astrometric Field (AF); (2) it should allow (some) astrophysical parameters to be determined, with emphasis on the dense sky regions where the Medium Band Photometer (MBP) becomes inefficient, such as the galactic plane and bulge.

The requirement for chromaticity calibration is probably satisfied for any broadband system with at least four bands, provided that they cover the whole spectral region of the AF (corresponding to the G magnitude).

For the astrophysical function there is no clear route how to arrive at an optimal photometric system. For the moment we can do little more than making some (educated?) guesses and testing these systems by standard classification/parameterisation methods.

In this document two systems are proposed, one 'simple' (called 2B) aiming mainly at continuum measurements, and another (3B) which is more demanding from a technical viewpoint but possibly with a much higher scientific potential. The parallel evaluation of these two systems could give some useful indications for future optimisation of the BBP.

The proposals are based on extensive comments and suggestions by Vladas Vansevicius, Jens Knude and Carme Jordi, which I gratefully acknowledge. The comments were received in response to a previous draft proposal (now to be called system 1B), which is not further considered here.

FIGURE 1: Reflectance for a single Ag coating (dashed) and after six reflections (dotted), together with the responses obtained with CCD sensitivity types #3 (standard) and #1B (blue-enhanced).

2 Assumptions

2.1 Mirrors, CCDs and integration times

For the Astro telescope it is assumed that silver (Ag) coating is used and that there are six reflections. The assumed reflectances are given in the accompanying text file LL045-G.dat (see also Fig. 1).

The standard quantum efficiency for the Astro instrument is assumed to be of type CCD#3, but the use of a blue-enhanced sensitivity type (CCD#1B) is also considered. The QE curves for both types (obtained by spline interpolation of the usual QE values at 50 nm intervals) are also given in LL045-G.dat, together with the resulting response functions (total transmittance times quantum efficiency). The response functions are shown in Fig. 1.

The integration time per CCD crossing is 3.315 s in the AF. For the BBP it may be 3.315 s or (usually) 1.915 s. If five slots are allotted to the BBP it is assumed that one gets 3.315 s and the remaining four get 1.915 s. For seven slots it is assumed that two get 3.315 s and five get 1.915 s (TBC).

2.2 Filter transmittances

The filter transmittance curves are assumed to be trapezoidal with slightly rounded corners. The sloping sides of adjacent bands overlap so that the sum of the transmittances is roughly constant. The transmittance at the maximum is assumed to be 0.90.

The short-wavelength cut-off of the bluest band and the long-wavelength cut-off of the reddest band are assumed to be completely determined by the mirror reflectances and the CCD QE, rather than by the filters; the corresponding parts of the filter curves are therefore left unspecified. This may not be possible (or even desirable) in the actual BBP design, in which case the counts in the extreme bands would be slightly reduced compared to present numbers.

2.3 Characterisation of response functions

For a given BBP band, the response function $R(\lambda)$ is defined as the product of the total telescope transmittance (or reflectance), the filter transmittance, and the CCD quantum efficiency. The function may be characterised by the following parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \int_0^\infty R(\lambda) d\lambda \\ \lambda_{\text{eff}} &= \frac{\int_0^\infty R(\lambda)\lambda d\lambda}{W} \\ \Delta\lambda &= \frac{W}{R_{\text{max}}} \end{aligned}$$

The parameter W is a measure of the total ‘throughput’ of the band, while λ_{eff} and $\Delta\lambda$ more or less correspond to the usual effective wavelength and FWHM (at least for the simple band shapes considered here). The product $W\tau$, where τ is the integration time in the band per Astro transit, is an indication of the ‘sensitivity’ of the photometer for the band in question (for fixed telescope aperture). For good determination of photometric indices it is generally desirable to balance the $W\tau$ among the bands.

The main characteristics of the proposed systems are given in Table 1.

3 Proposed BBP systems

3.1 General considerations

For a $V = 20$ star at $\lambda = 550$ nm, the typical photoelectron count in the BBP is of order 1 count per nm bandwidth (FWHM). Accumulated over the mission (82 transits on average) this means that reasonable precisions (~ 0.01 mag) at the limiting magnitude can only be achieved with broad-band filter systems (FWHM ~ 100 nm). Thus, apart from

TABLE 1: Main characteristics of the BBP systems 2B and 3B. λ_{lo} and λ_{hi} are the low and high wavelengths at half-maximum filter transmittance; W , λ_{eff} and $\Delta\lambda$ are defined in Sect. 2.3; τ is the integration time per Astro FOV transit. $W\tau$ is a measure of the total ‘sensitivity’ of the band for a spectrum that is flat in terms of photons per wavelength unit.

System	Band	Filter $\lambda_{lo}/\lambda_{hi}$	CCD type	W [nm]	λ_{eff} [nm]	$\Delta\lambda$ [nm]	τ [s]	$W\tau$ [nm s]
2B	B45	/490	3	28	453	72	3.315	93
2B	B56	500/615	3	68	561	107	1.915	130
2B	B67	610/735	3	86	674	122	1.915	165
2B	B80	735/880	3	85	803	136	1.915	163
2B	B93	880/	3	45	932	129	1.915	86
3B	B41	/450	1B	30	411	78	2×1.915	115
3B	B51	450/575	1B	67	515	119	1.915	128
3B	B67	575/775	3	134	676	192	1.915	257
3B	B87	775/	3	104	871	180	1.915	199
3B	M51	495/525	1B	17	510	31	2×3.315	113

general continuum slopes and discontinuities, only very strong spectral features (perhaps the Mg/MgH feature at 510 nm) could profitably be measured with the BBP.

Given the intrinsic ‘unobservability’ of most spectral signatures other than those caused by temperature and/or extinction, it makes sense to design the BBP system such that T_{eff} and A_V can be determined (preferably separately) as well as possible.¹ In this case it is desirable to minimise the effects of the other main parameters ($\log g$ and $[M/H]$), i.e. one should attempt to measure the continuum and avoid the strong line complexes.

On the other hand, if more integration time can be used for the BBP, one could still consider the measurement of one or a few features sensitive to gravity and/or metallicity. Contrary to the previous philosophy, at least some band should be centred on such line complexes and the bandwidth should be tailored to that feature. Some bands for temperature/extinction measurement are of course still required. For sensitivity to metallicity it is also generally desirable to go to shorter wavelengths than is needed for continuum measurements.

The two BBP systems proposed here more or less follow the two different philosophies outlined above. System 2B is ‘merely’ intended to measure temperature and/or extinction, while 3B has some bands that are potentially useful for other parameters, in particular metallicity. The systems also differ in complexity and expensiveness (not least in terms of integration time), in that 3B requires two more slots for the BBP and the use of two different CCD sensitivity types. It is interesting to evaluate how much can be gained, scientifically, by such added complexity.

¹VV argues that the determination of astrophysical parameters for images that are blended in the MBP would be highly facilitated if the temperatures could be resolved in the BBP.

FIGURE 2: Response functions (i.e., total transmittance times quantum efficiency) for system 2B. The bands are designated B45, B56, B67, B80, B93 as in Table 1.

3.2 System 2B

System 2B was proposed by Vasevicius (private communication, 15 April 2003) replacing an earlier proposal by Lindegren (system 1B, no longer considered). It has five bands roughly centred on 450, 560, 670, 800 and 930 nm. It is designed to give a good continuum estimate over as wide a spectral range as permitted by the Ag coating in combination with the standard CCD sensitivity type (#3) currently foreseen for the AF.

The system is similar to a standard *BVRI* system with an added band at 930 nm. The low response below 400 nm makes the system relatively insensitive to the Balmer discontinuity as well as to the Ca H and K lines. Similarly, the placement of the break between the two bluest bands near the Mg feature at 510 nm makes the corresponding colour index ($B45 - B56 \simeq B - V$) rather insensitive to this feature. Some sensitivity to metallicity remains however e.g. through the G band at 430 nm.

The filter transmittances and the total response functions for system 2B are given in file LL045-2B.dat. The response functions are plotted in Fig. 2. Representative counts are given in Table 2.

3.3 System 3B

This system is partly modelled after the well-known Washington photometric system (Cantenna, AJ 81, 228, 1976), which uses four bands called *C*, *M*, *T1* and *T2*. With an added intermediate band at the 510 nm Mg/MgH feature (Greisen, PASP 96, 723, 1984) this

FIGURE 3: Response functions (i.e., total transmittance times quantum efficiency) for system 3B. The bands are designated B41, B51, B67, B87 (solid curves) and M51 (dashed) as in Table 1.

system has been used extensively for photometric surveys of galactic populations (halo, bulge), clusters and dwarf spheroidal galaxies. The 510 nm band was originally added mainly to discriminate between distant giants and foreground dwarfs. For GAIA it is likely that this discrimination can be made entirely from the astrometry, in which case the addition of such a band may seem a waste of integration time. However, Knude (draft note 9 April 2003) has shown that the Mg index could also be a powerful indicator of metallicity, especially for giants, where it retains good sensitivity even for very metal-poor stars.

The Washington *C* band has an effective wavelength of 391 nm and a FWHM of 110 nm (i.e., covering roughly 336 to 446 nm). This interval includes a number of CN bands (360, 388, 422 nm), the G band around 430 nm, and numerous metallic lines. The Washington *M* band (effective wavelength 508 nm, FWHM 105 nm, i.e., roughly covering the interval 456 to 561 nm) includes many metallic lines but is specifically designed to avoid the CN and G bands. Thus, an important feature of the Washington system seems to be that the separation wavelength between *C* and *M* is just longward of the G band at 430 nm. The remaining two bands *T1* (593–673 nm) and *T2* (719–859 nm) in the Washington system are mainly for temperature determination and could probably just as well be, for instance, the *R* and *I* bands.² Based on these considerations, the separation wavelength for the first two bands of system 3B was set at 450 nm, while the two remaining bands were made to cover the rest of the wavelength region in the AF. In order to improve the UV sensitivity of the first band (B41 \simeq *C*) and the throughput of the second (B51 \simeq *M*), a CCD sensitivity

²There is however the additional feature that the CN bands around 680–750 nm fall in the overlap region of *T1* and *T2* and therefore do not affect the temperature index *T1* – *T2* too much.

TABLE 2: Representative counts for a $V = 15$ magnitude star in one Astro transit for the BBP systems 2B and 3B. Based on Kurucz (1993) models with the following $(T_{\text{eff}}, \log g, [\text{Fe}/\text{H}])$: A0V = (9500, 4.5, 0), F0V = (7500, 4.5, 0), G0V = (6000, 4.5, 0), K2V = (5000, 4.5, 0), K7V = (4000, 4.5, 0), K5III = (4000, 1.5, 0). No extinction is assumed.

System	Band	A0V	F0V	G0V	K2V	K7V	K5III
2B	B45	8890	7172	5765	4719	3398	3161
2B	B56	8935	9172	9417	9727	10409	10227
2B	B67	7686	9391	11364	13644	18315	18045
2B	B80	5316	7302	9898	13100	22334	21138
2B	B93	2204	3064	4457	6425	12968	12228
3B	B41	11029	8111	5567	3576	2190	1651
3B	B51	10249	9549	8974	8484	7472	7521
3B	B67	12189	14772	17774	21301	29051	28380
3B	B87	5662	7893	11129	15389	28838	27121
3B	M51	9061	8393	7723	6803	4731	5381

type #1B was selected for these bands (as well as for the intermediate band M51). The separation between B67 and B87 was rather arbitrarily set at 775 nm.

The intermediate band M51 is centred on 510 nm and has a FWHM of 30 nm. This is wider than the Geisler (DDO51) band but similar to F51 in the Geneva–Barcelona MBP system. M51 – B51 provides an almost reddening-free index of the Mg/MgH feature.

The filter transmittances and the total response functions for system 3B are given in file LL045-3B.dat. The response functions are plotted in Fig. 3. Representative counts are given in Table 2.

4 Conclusion

The two BBP systems 2B and 3B are proposed for further study with regard to classification and astrophysical parameterisation.